

THE BASICS OF ORGANIZING EDUCATION AIMED AT INCREASING THE VARIOUS COMPETENCIES OF STUDENTS OF TECHNICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Saparova Ayzada Alauatdin qi'zi'

1st stage doctoral student of

Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz

Annotation: Preparation of engineers for professional activity in technical higher educational institutions and scientific research institutions, expansion of professionally oriented theoretical tasks related to students' educational and research activities, principles and criteria of selection of educational content and their improvement, training of students creating an environment for active practical and creative assimilation of universal human culture, integration of humanitarian and natural-scientific knowledge and establishment of interdisciplinary relations are being carried out. This article discusses such issues.

Keywords: competence, professionally competent, engineer, problem, expert, development, quality.

INTRODUCTION

The stage of development of professional competence of students of technical higher education institutions in the educational system places high demands on the student's professional training, professional skills, intellectual potential, knowledge, skills and qualifications [3,4,5]. In later times, the importance of professional training and the knowledge gained in this process and fundamental sciences can be seen in all areas related to activity: modern production, discovery design, research, theoretical aspects of psychological-pedagogical approaches and other areas [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Development of professional competence of students of technical higher education institutions, creativity, logical thinking, independent preparation, scientific research ability, appreciation of spiritual and scientific values, critical thinking, management skills in future engineers in solving problems arising in professional activity using fundamental sciences. and at the same time develops the professional competence of future engineers [2]. The quality of fundamental knowledge of engineers has always been in the center of attention of the community of higher education institutions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The development of professional competence of students of higher educational institutions requires the implementation of professional activities in a certain specialty. In the process of mastering professional activities, it is important to have the ability to implement an analytical approach to the mastery of fundamental sciences, as well as the ability to clarify and develop fundamental knowledge to a certain extent [3].

The purpose of teaching basic sciences in technical higher education institutions is to acquire the skills and competences to identify, analyze and evaluate the problems of learning these sciences, and to study the practical value of the acquired knowledge and apply it in professional activities. consists of teaching [3]. In the teaching of fundamental sciences, the goals of developing practical knowledge of reproductive, productive and creative nature in future engineers on the basis of reflexive subject activities, forming motivations for educational and professional activity are directly related to the competence of a technical specialist. The following tasks arise from these goals:

- development of fundamental training of future engineers in order to develop professional qualities;
- by teaching fundamental sciences to students, to develop their concepts and ideas related to professional activity

- improvement of professional-practical (problem-active, creative) issues in students based on leveling, comparison, analysis and synthesis, abstraction, generalization and establishment of interdisciplinary connections through independent analysis of educational resources based on a creative approach.

- development of students' ability to present the learning material they have mastered through various methods;

- development of research abilities of future engineers by actively including them in the educational process.

One of the important laws of the educational process in higher education institutions is the law of interdisciplinarity. Interdisciplinarity in the training of engineers is the connection of the vocational training course with the fundamental-general technical and special courses. By mastering fundamental sciences, future engineers will achieve scientific and creative solutions to problems arising in their professional activities, and scientific creativity will develop their logical, critical and creative thinking skills in solving problems.

The following requirements can be expressed for the content of the development of the fundamental knowledge of future engineers: paying special attention to the departments of fundamental sciences that serve to develop the professional competence of the graduate taking into account the future profession, to include elements of professional tasks that require the practical application of the acquired knowledge [5], to have the necessary fundamental knowledge to solve theoretical and practical problems. The goal of developing the professional competence of students of technical higher education institutions is, firstly, that the student acquires fundamental training related to a specific professional activity (knowledge, skills and qualifications), and secondly, it is to improve the competence of applying the acquired knowledge in practice.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above considerations, it can be said that the development of professional competence of students of technical higher education institutions

envisages the formation of the skills of applying the knowledge they have acquired in fundamental sciences to their professional activities. When the content of students' knowledge and skills is suitable for the future production activity, and when it forms a system of integrity with the content of general technical and special sciences, it helps more effectively in developing a system of certain important professional qualities in future engineers.

This shows that the development of such competencies of graduates of technical higher education institutions mainly depends on the level of their acquisition of fundamental knowledge.

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